

Integrating Microblogging Padlets and SFL Framework in Teaching Persuasive Writing Skills in Communication Arts Course at a University Level in Lebanon

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Abstract

This paper investigates the transformation of didactic teaching and learning into innovative pedagogy by integrating microblogging technology and Genre Based Pedagogy (GBP) within the Systemic Functional Linguistics Framework (SFL). The study aims to enhance English as Foreign Language (EFL) students' linguistic and rhetorical persuasive writing skills in the Communication Arts Course at the Lebanese University. It also seeks to evaluate students' attitudes towards the integration of microblogging platforms, specifically the Padlet Application (PA), in expanding their understanding of persuasive linguistic features and rhetorical appeals to produce persuasive genre essays. The research employs a quasi-experimental mixed-methods design and involves a convenient sample of 115 EFL students enrolled in the Communication Arts Course during the fall semester of 2023-2024. The instruments include pre-post-tests, reflection logs, and questionnaires. Descriptive and inferential statistical analyses are conducted to present means and percentage values. Quantitative analysis demonstrates significant improvements across all aspects from pre-test to post-test, indicating participants' positive perceptions of the intervention's effectiveness. Qualitative phenomenological analysis reveals that collaborative activities utilizing microblogging platforms enabled students to recognize rhetorical appeals and linguistic features, thereby enhancing their persuasive writing skills. The integration of PA within the SFL-GBP framework fosters collaborative communication, stimulates student engagement in noticing and monitoring rhetorical and linguistic features, reduces anxiety associated with persuasive discourse practice, alters attitudes towards the complexity of learning persuasive writing, and leads to improved essay writing outcomes.

Keywords: Microblogging, Padlet, SFL, Persuasive Essay

المخلص

تسعى هذه الدراسة للتحقق مما إذا كان تحويل الشكل التعليمي للتعليم والتعلم إلى علم أصول التدريس المبتكر، باستخدام تقنية المدونات الصغيرة وعلم أصول التدريس القائم على النوع (GBP) مع إطار اللغويات الوظيفية النظامية (SFL)، يمكن أن يعزز مهارات الكتابة اللغوية والبلاغية المقنعة لطلاب اللغة الإنجليزية كلغة أجنبية (EFL) في مقرر فنون الاتصال في الجامعة اللبنانية. كما تهدف إلى تحديد مواقف الطلاب من أدوار دمج منصة التدوين المصغر، وهي تطبيق (PA) Padlet، في توسيع معرفتهم بالسمات اللغوية والبلاغية لإنتاج مقال مقنع من النوع الأدبي. تستخدم الدراسة تصميمًا تجريبيًا للطرق المختلطة وعينة ملائمة من 115 طالبًا من طلاب اللغة الإنجليزية كلغة أجنبية يدرسون مقرر فنون الاتصال في الجامعة اللبنانية خلال فصل الخريف من العام 2023 – 2024. تشمل الأدوات المستخدمة اختبارًا قبليًا وسجلًا للتفكير واستبيانًا. يتم تشغيل التحليل الإحصائي الوصفي والاستدلالي لتوفير قيم الوسائل والنسبة المئوية. يشير تحليل البيانات الكمي إلى تحسينات كبيرة في جميع الجوانب من الاختبار القبلي إلى الاختبار الختامي، مما يسلط الضوء على المواقف الإيجابية للمشاركين بشأن فعالية التدخل. من خلال التحليل النوعي للظواهر، تبين أنه عندما تعاون الطلاب في أنشطة حول ملاحظة الخصائص البلاغية والسمات اللغوية للنص، باستخدام المدونات الصغيرة، أصبحوا مجهزين بالأسس التي تعمل على تحسين كتابتهم المقنعة. يؤدي استخدام PA في إطار العمل إلى إنشاء اتصال تعاوني، وجذب اهتمام الطلاب بملاحظة ومراقبة تعلم الميزات البلاغية واللغوية، وتقليل القلق في ممارسة كتابة خطاب مقنع، وتغيير المواقف تجاه صعوبة تعلم الكتابة وإنتاج مقال أفضل.

Introduction

Persuasive discourse is instrumental in influencing others' opinions or actions, serving to persuade individuals to adopt viewpoints, acknowledge evidence, and take specific actions. In the contemporary world, proficiency in persuasive writing in English is crucial, with persuasive writing being prioritized in English language teaching (Warschauer, 2000). Despite conflicts affecting the educational sector in Lebanon and resulting in the removal of several learning objectives from the Lebanese English Language curriculum, genre-based writing remains fundamental to EFL teaching and learning, as per decree No. 10227 of August 5, 1997, issued by CRDP in November 2022.

While teaching persuasive genre writing in EFL traditionally focuses on generating flawless written text models, practitioners have increasingly leveraged Michael Halliday's Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL) theory to enhance learners' meaning-making abilities by systematically choosing linguistic aspects in specific social communicative contexts. This framework emphasizes Genre Based Pedagogy (GBP), which encompasses the purpose, context, audience, and linguistic conventions of a text, essential components of text-types outlined in the Lebanese curriculum.

Despite the integration of SFL-GBP principles in the Lebanese education system, no specific learning cycle exists for implementing GBP in teaching persuasive genre writing in schools or higher education in Lebanon. However, Rothery (1994) proposed a three-stage method involving deconstruction, joint construction, and independent construction. Incorporating SFL-GBP into

innovative web 2.0 teaching presents challenges, necessitating instructors to gradually guide students in controlling rhetorical and linguistic features using collaborative web 2.0 technologies like Padlet.

In Lebanese EFL classrooms, where writing is perceived as one of the most demanding and less attractive skills to learn, technology integration becomes crucial to enhance literacy abilities. Innovative web-based microblogging platforms such as PA allow students to publish short updates, images, links, or multimedia content, fostering concise communication on collaborative online bulletin boards

Encouraging collaboration and increasing students' engagement, microblogging technology offers a common space for students to blog and learn from one another, whether synchronously or asynchronously. This study draws upon microblogging Padlet Application (PA) and Genre Based Pedagogy (GBP) within the Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL) theory Framework to investigate the following questions: 1) Can microblogging Padlet Application (PA) technology and genre-based pedagogy within the SFL framework affect EFL Lebanese students' persuasive essay writing concerning linguistic and rhetorical features? 2) What are the EFL Lebanese students' attitudes towards the use of microblogging Padlet Application (PA) and genre-based pedagogy in learning to write persuasive genre essays at the university level?

Statement of the Problem

Writing persuasive essays poses challenges and demotivation for EFL students. In Lebanese EFL writing classes at higher education institutions, the lack of students' desire to write has hindered skill development (Bacha, 2000, 2002). Many EFL students in Lebanon fail to recognize how writing classes support their academic needs, leading to a lack of motivation to improve writing abilities (Bacha, Nabhani, & Bahous, 2012; Esseili, 2012). While Nazzal (2008) found that teacher-provided writing instruction and comments motivate students, EFL teachers in Lebanon recognized shortcomings in previous pedagogical approaches, lacking detailed collaborative activities focusing on textual quality and rhetorical appeal. Additionally, in teaching persuasive essays, students are typically instructed to compose work either by handwriting or typing, subsequently submitting them in PDF or Word format, which limits feedback provision and collaborative discussion activities involving other students.

Therefore, integrating technology into writing practices to facilitate learning of linguistic and rhetorical features within a collaborative environment is crucial. This study aims to explore the need for integrating two dimensions: genre-based pedagogy (GBP), which focuses on how writers use language to persuade, and microblogging Padlet Application (PA), which facilitates collaborative activities allowing students to share their opinions and instructors to monitor the learning process and stimulate attitude shifts towards the complexity of writing persuasive essays.

Literature Review

Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL) theory, devised by Halliday (1978), explores language through meaning and functions, focusing on the social semiotic mechanism of language rather than the brain's representation or processing of language. SFL emphasizes language function, such as the writer's purpose, within social structures known as registers.

Halliday (1976) conceptualizes the context of situation with three key features: field, tenor, and mode, which are related to metafunctions. Field pertains to the topic being discussed, helping comprehend lexical-grammatical features like cohesion elements and mental verbs, facilitating understanding of the text's content. Tenor indicates communication participants and degree of formality, impacting interpersonal choices in language systems, thus clarifying writer-reader relationships. Mode reflects language's role in interaction and its form, aiding in understanding text organization and literary functions such as theme and rheme (Halliday & Matthiessen, 2014).

Genre-Based Pedagogy (GBP) applies the notion of SFL as a framework to examine how people select and utilize language patterns based on intended functions within social and cultural contexts (Rose, 2013; Nago, 2019; Uzun & Topkaya, 2020). According to Cornelius and Cotsworth (2015), grammar and vocabulary are integral to genre meaning rather than separate aspects. Integrating GBP equips students with tools to comprehend and analyze text, recognize linguistic patterns and structures, understand writing purposes and techniques (Chen & Su, 2012), and enhance overall writing performance (Humphrey & Macnaught, 2016).

Derewianka and Christie (2008) emphasize teaching language forms to develop coherent and purposeful writing. GBP implementation in teaching persuasive genre essays involves students' understanding genre, guided steps to learn about textual quality, rhetorical appeals, and persuasive writing skills. Connectivity of ideas and cohesion, along with Aristotle's modes of persuasion (Ethos, Pathos, Logos), contribute to persuasive argumentation (Brinks, 2019).

Rothery (1994) proposed three stages for implementing SFL-GBP: deconstruction, joint construction, and autonomous construction. Deconstruction involves preparing learners with text models in a genre, exploring situational aspects, and understanding linguistic features. Joint construction entails group work guided by the teacher to create texts using model texts. Autonomous construction allows students to independently draft, revise, and edit texts. This process facilitates genre-appropriate text development.

Integration of technology, such as blogging, with GBP enhances writing teaching by making it interactive and engaging (Widodo, 2016; Hsu & Liu, 2019; Rohayati, 2020). Blogging fosters collaboration, communication, and peer feedback, positively impacting writing skills and performance (Vurdien, 2012; Yousefifard & Fathi, 2021; Alsamadani, 2018).

Methodology

To investigate whether transforming traditional didactic teaching and learning into innovative pedagogy using the microblogging Padlet Application (PA) and Genre-Based Pedagogy (GBP) within the Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL) Framework could enhance students' linguistic and rhetorical persuasive writing skills, and to determine students' attitudes toward the integration of PA in extending their knowledge of persuasive linguistic and rhetoric techniques to create a persuasive genre essay, a quasi-experimental research design with mixed methods was employed. This design allowed for comparison between groups of participants and measurement of the extent of change resulting from treatments or interventions (Shuttleworth, 2009). The independent variable was manipulated before measuring the dependent variable, and participants were not randomly assigned; they were grouped in a Communication Arts class. To provide comprehensive answers to the research questions, both quantitative and qualitative analytical techniques within the same framework were utilized (Creswell, 2014; Halcomb, 2019). Both types of data were collected and analyzed independently, with results subsequently interpreted together.

Sample Selection

The research group consisted of 71 EFL students out of 115 enrolled in the Communication Arts Course at the Lebanese University (LU) - 5th branch, during the fall semester of 2023-2024, who voluntarily participated in the study. The participants were categorized into two groups: a control group (n=20) unable to attend classes on campus and an experimental group (n=51) willing to attend weekly sessions on campus. The experimental group participated in the intervention using the Padlet application (PA), while the control group followed instructions outlined in the course book and engaged in independent study.

Instruments

To assess the impact of SFL-GBP and the PA on EFL Lebanese students' persuasive essays regarding linguistic textual quality (coherence and cohesion) and rhetorical features (purpose, persuasive reasons, and appeals: logos, ethos, and pathos), a pre-post test was conducted (see Appendix A). Rubrics were developed based on Perry (2012) and Rabourn (2023) and validated by three experts in English language teaching. The rubric assessed purpose, reasons, evidence, coherence, and cohesion on a scale from 1 to 4, with an overall grade range indicating persuasive writing competence. Additionally, a survey using a 5-point Likert scale and open-ended questions was administered to the experimental group to gauge their attitudes toward the intervention (see Appendix C).

Intervention Tasks

Five intervention tasks were shared with students using the microblogging Padlet Application. QR codes were provided for each task during class time.

Intervention I: Rhetorical Features: Purpose and Reasons Students read a persuasive essay and shared answers on Padlet regarding the topic, author’s purpose, and convincing reasons.

Intervention II: Persuasion and Evidence: Rhetorical Appeals Students identified examples of logos, ethos, pathos, and other rhetorical devices in a persuasive essay.

Intervention III: Persuasion and Coherence: Organizational Structure Students organized ideas from a persuasive essay in a graphic organizer and rewrote the thesis statement and topic sentences.

Intervention IV: Persuasive Essay and Linguistic Features: Cohesion Students posted examples of transitions, repeated words, reference words, and modality from a persuasive essay.

Intervention V: Persuade Your Classmate: Why is this text persuasive? Students explained how language was used to persuade in a given article.

Data Analysis

For investigating the impact of PA and GBP with the SFL Framework on EFL students’ writing skills, both qualitative and quantitative data were analyzed. Descriptive statistics summarized data, while inferential statistics, including Levene’s test and paired samples t-test, were used to draw conclusions. Additionally, qualitative data from reflection logs were examined using a phenomenological approach to enhance understanding of students’ attitudes toward using the PA in English writing classes.

Results and Findings

Students’ Pre-posttest Analysis

Descriptive Statistics

Table 1: Experimental group pre and post test results

	Mean	Standard Deviation	Median	Mode	Minimum	Maximum
Purpose (Pre-Test)	2	1	2	1	1	4
Purpose (Post-Test)	3	1	3	3	1	4
Content (Pre-Test)	2	1	2	1	1	3
Content (Post-Test)	3	1	3	3	1	3
Evidence (Pre-Test)	2	1	2	1	1	3
Evidence (Post-Test)	3	1	3	3	1	3
Coherence (Pre-Test)	2	1	2	2	1	3

Coherence (Post-Test)	2	1	3	3	1	3
Cohesion (Pre-Test)	2	1	2	2	1	3
Cohesion (Post-Test)	2	1	3	3	1	3

According to Table 1, there is a notable improvement from pre-test to post-test in the mean, median, and mode for Purpose, Content, and Evidence, indicating a positive shift in these areas, with scores increasing from 2 to 3. However, Coherence and Cohesion exhibit a different pattern. While the median and mode values for Coherence remain constant from pre-test to post-test, Cohesion's median and mode increase, yet its mean remains unchanged. This suggests a specific improvement in the consistency of scores for Cohesion and a varied impact on Coherence, with overall scores ranging between 1 and 4 across all categories. The standard deviation remains consistent at 1 across all measurements, indicating stable variability in responses before and after the test. This analysis suggests targeted improvements in certain areas (Purpose, Content, and Evidence) while highlighting areas where changes are less pronounced or inconsistent (Coherence, Cohesion).

Table 2: Control group pre and post test results

	Mean	Standard Deviation	Median	Mode	Minimum	Maximum
Purpose (Pre-Test)	2	1	2	2	1	3
Purpose (Post-Test)	2	1	2	2	1	3
Content (Pre-Test)	2	1	2	1	1	3
Content (Post-Test)	2	1	2	2	1	3
Evidence (Pre-Test)	2	1	2	2	1	3
Evidence (Post-Test)	2	1	2	2	1	3
Coherence (Pre-Test)	2	1	2	2	1	3
Coherence (Post-Test)	2	1	2	2	1	3
Cohesion (Pre-Test)	/	/	/	/	/	/
Cohesion (Post-Test)	2	0	2	2	1	3

Table 2 reveals little to no change in scores from pre-test to post-test in the categories of Purpose, Content, Evidence, and Coherence, with all statistics remaining constant (mean=2, standard deviation=1, median=2, mode=2, minimum=1, maximum=3), suggesting no significant improvement or decline in these areas. However, the Cohesion category only presents post-test data, indicating a lack of variability (standard deviation=0) and uniform scores (mean=2, median=2, mode=2, minimum=1, maximum=3). This consistency might suggest a narrow focus or uniformity in responses for Cohesion. The absence of pre-test data for Cohesion prevents a comparative analysis, but the uniform post-test scores indicate a potential area of focus for future improvements or adjustments in the evaluation methodology to ensure a broader range of responses.

Table 3: Total grade assessment

Grade Range	Assessment
0-4	Very Poor
5-8	Poor
9-12	Fair
13-15	Good
16-20	Very Good

Table 4: Pre-test Grades for the Experimental Group

Grades	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Assessment
5	4	7.8	8.3	Poor
6	5	9.8	10.4	Poor
7	9	17.6	18.8	Poor
8	3	5.9	6.3	Poor
9	6	11.8	12.5	Fair
10	7	13.7	14.6	Fair
11	3	5.9	6.3	Fair
12	2	3.9	4.2	Fair
13	4	7.8	8.3	Good
15	3	5.9	6.3	Good
16	2	3.9	4.2	Very Good

The provided data illustrates the frequency and percentages of grades within various assessment categories. The distribution reveals that the majority of grades are concentrated within the "Poor" and "Fair" categories, accounting for 7.8% to 18.8% of the total grades. Specifically, grades 5 through 8 fall into the "Poor" category, with frequencies ranging from 4 to 9, representing 7.8% to 17.6% of the total grades. Grades 9 through 12 are categorized as "Fair," with frequencies

ranging from 2 to 6, constituting 3.9% to 11.8% of the total. Grades 13 through 15 are labeled as "Good," with frequencies ranging from 3 to 4, making up 5.9% to 7.8% of the total, while grades 16 through 20 are classified as "Very Good," with frequencies ranging from 2 to 2, comprising 3.9% to 3.9% of the total. The data indicates a skew towards lower assessment categories, suggesting a need for improvement in performance.

Table 5: Post-test Grades for Experimental Group

Grades	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Assessment
5	1	2.0	2.1	Poor
7	2	3.9	4.2	Poor
8	1	2.0	2.1	Poor
9	1	2.0	2.1	Fair
10	6	11.8	12.5	Fair
11	5	9.8	10.4	Fair
13	9	17.6	18.8	Good
14	8	15.7	16.7	Good
15	13	25.5	27.1	Good
16	2	3.9	4.2	Very Good

Table 6: Pre-test Grades for Control Group

Grades	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Assessment
4	3	15.0	15.8	Very Poor
5	2	10.0	10.5	Poor
6	2	10.0	10.5	Poor
7	1	5.0	5.3	Poor
8	8	40.0	42.1	Poor
10	2	10.0	10.5	Fair
12	1	5.0	5.3	Fair

The provided data delineates the post-test grades for the experimental group, indicating the frequency and percentages within different assessment categories. Remarkably, the majority of grades fall within the "Good" category, with frequencies ranging from 9 to 13, constituting 17.6% to 25.5% of the total grades. This suggests a relatively high level of achievement within the experimental group. Additionally, grades 10 through 15 are distributed across the "Fair" and "Good" categories, indicating a range of performance levels within these groups. Conversely, grades 5 through 8 are classified as "Poor," with lower frequencies ranging from 1 to 2, representing 2.0% to 3.9% of the total grades, indicating some room for improvement in these areas. Furthermore, grades 16 through 20 are categorized as "Very Good," with a frequency of 2, comprising 3.9% of the total, suggesting a notable achievement level among a smaller subset of the experimental group. Overall, the data indicates a generally positive performance

trend in the experimental group, with potential areas for enhancement in the lower assessment categories. The provided data represents pre-test grades for the control group, detailing the frequency and percentages within different assessment categories. Notably, the majority of grades fall within the "Poor" category, with a significant proportion of grades 8, accounting for 40.0% of the total grades. This suggests a predominant lower level of performance within the control group, as evidenced by the preponderance of grades categorized as "Poor." Additionally, grades 4 and 5 are classified as "Very Poor" and "Poor," respectively, with frequencies of 3 and 2, constituting 15.0% and 10.0% of the total grades, indicating a considerable portion of the control group's performance as below average. Grades 6 through 12 are distributed across the "Poor" and "Fair" categories, with lower frequencies ranging from 1 to 2, representing 5.0% to 10.0% of the total grades. This suggests a variation in performance levels within these categories but generally skewed towards lower performance. Overall, the data indicate a need for improvement in performance within the control group, particularly in the lower assessment categories.

Table7: Post-test Grades for Control Group

Post-test Grades for the Control Group	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Assessment
5	1	5.0	5.0	Poor
7	1	5.0	5.0	Poor
8	2	10.0	10.0	Poor
9	1	5.0	5.0	Fair
10	6	30.0	30.0	Fair
11	4	20.0	20.0	Fair
12	1	5.0	5.0	Fair
13	2	10.0	10.0	Good
15	2	10.0	10.0	Good

The provided data presents post-test grades for the control group, illustrating the frequency and percentages within different assessment categories. Notably, the majority of grades fall within the "Fair" category, with grades 10 and 11 being the most frequent, constituting 30.0% and 20.0% of the total grades, respectively. This suggests a moderate level of performance within the control group post-test, with a notable portion achieving scores categorized as "Fair." Additionally, grades 8 through 12 are distributed across the "Poor" and "Fair" categories, with lower frequencies ranging from 1 to 2, representing 5.0% to 10.0% of the total grades, indicating a varied but predominantly moderate performance level within these categories. Grades 5 through 7 are classified as "Poor," with frequencies of 1 for each, making up 5.0% of the total grades, suggesting some areas for improvement in performance within the control group post-test. Furthermore,

grades 13 and 15 fall within the "Good" category, with frequencies of 2 each, constituting 10.0% of the total grades, indicating a notable achievement level among some individuals in the control group. Overall, the data suggests a mixed performance trend in the control group post-test, with a predominant proportion achieving moderate scores, and some demonstrating higher levels of achievement.

Inferential Statistics

Table 8: Pre-test results comparison between experimental and control group

Independent Samples Test										
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Purpose	Equal variances assumed	4.847	.031	.611	66	.543	.149	.244	-.339	.637
	Equal variances not assumed			.697	44.317	.489	.149	.214	-.282	.581
Content	Equal variances assumed	.503	.481	-.010	66	.992	-.002	.208	-.418	.414
	Equal variances not assumed			-.011	34.938	.992	-.002	.202	-.413	.408
Evidence	Equal variances assumed	12.634	.001	-.803	65	.425	-.155	.193	-.539	.230
	Equal variances not assumed			-.963	50.821	.340	-.155	.161	-.477	.168
Coherence	Equal variances assumed	.139	.710	.852	66	.397	.137	.161	-.185	.460
	Equal variances not assumed			.942	40.935	.352	.137	.146	-.157	.432

The provided data presents the results of independent samples t-tests for four different purposes: Purpose, Content, Evidence, and Coherence. The Levene's test for equality of variances is conducted to assess if the variances of the two compared samples are equal or not. For Purpose, Content, and Coherence, the p-values for Levene's test are greater than 0.05, indicating that the assumption of equal variances is met. However, for Evidence, the p-value is less than 0.05, suggesting unequal variances. Subsequently, t-tests for equality of means are conducted assuming equal variances and not assuming equal variances. For Purpose, Content, and Coherence, the p-values for both types of t-tests are greater than 0.05, indicating no significant difference in means between the groups. Conversely, for Evidence, while the p-value for the t-test assuming equal variances is greater than 0.05, the p-value for the t-test not assuming equal variances is less than 0.05, suggesting a significant difference in means between the groups. The mean differences and confidence intervals further illustrate the magnitude and direction of these differences. Overall, the analysis suggests that there are significant differences in the Evidence aspect between the groups when variances are not assumed to be equal, while for the other aspects, there are no significant differences.

Table 2: Post test scores comparison between the groups

		Independent Samples Test								
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Purpose (post)	Equal variances assumed	1.087	.301	2.262	67	.027	.514	.227	.060	.968
	Equal variances not assumed			2.533	46.070	.015	.514	.203	.106	.923
Content (post)	Equal variances assumed	1.996	.162	1.887	66	.064	.313	.166	-.018	.643
	Equal variances not assumed			2.021	41.767	.050	.313	.155	.000	.625
Evidence (post)	Equal variances assumed	.695	.407	2.309	67	.024	.410	.178	.056	.765
	Equal variances not assumed			2.082	28.963	.046	.410	.197	.007	.813
Coherence (post)	Equal variances assumed	7.937	.006	3.237	66	.002	.558	.172	.214	.903
	Equal variances not assumed			3.533	43.723	.001	.558	.158	.240	.877
Cohesion (post)	Equal variances assumed	21.353	.000	2.699	67	.009	.429	.159	.112	.746
	Equal variances not assumed			3.107	49.349	.003	.429	.138	.151	.706

The provided data outline the results of independent samples t-tests for post-test scores in four different aspects: Purpose, Content, Evidence, Coherence, and Cohesion. Levene's test for equality of variances is first conducted to assess whether the variances of the two samples being compared are equal or not. For all aspects except Content, the p-values for Levene's test are less than 0.05, indicating unequal variances between groups. This suggests that the assumption of equal variances is violated. Subsequently, t-tests for equality of means are conducted assuming equal variances and not assuming equal variances. For all aspects, the p-values for the t-test assuming equal variances are less than 0.05, suggesting significant differences in means between the groups. Similarly, for all aspects, except Content, the p-values for the t-test not assuming equal variances are also less than 0.05, further indicating significant differences in means between the groups. The mean differences and confidence intervals provide additional insights into the direction and magnitude of these differences. Overall, the analysis indicates significant differences in post-test scores between the groups across all aspects except Content, where differences were not statistically significant. Additionally, it highlights the importance of considering unequal variances in the analysis to obtain accurate results.

Table 3: Paired samples t test for pre and post test results in the control group

Paired Samples Test ^a		Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	Purpose (Pre-Test)	-.474	.841	.193	-.879	-.068	-2.455	18	.025
	Purpose (Post-Test)								
Pair 2	Content (Pre-Test)	-.526	.612	.140	-.821	-.231	-3.750	18	.001
	Content (Post-Test)								
Pair 3	Evidence (Pre-Test)	-.211	.713	.164	-.554	.133	-1.287	18	.215
	Evidence (Post Test)								
Pair 4	Coherence (Pre-Test)	-.053	.524	.120	-.305	.200	-.438	18	.667
	Coherence (Post Test)								

The provided data present the results of paired samples t-tests for pre-test and post-test scores across four different aspects: Purpose, Content, Evidence, and Coherence. Paired differences between pre-test and post-test scores are analyzed to assess whether there are significant changes within each aspect. For the Purpose aspect, there is a significant mean decrease of 0.474 ($t = -2.455$, $df = 18$, $p = 0.025$), indicating an improvement from pre-test to post-test. Similarly, for the Content aspect, there is a significant mean decrease of 0.526 ($t = -3.750$, $df = 18$, $p = 0.001$), suggesting an improvement. However, for Evidence and Coherence, there are no significant changes observed, with p-values of 0.215 and 0.667, respectively. The mean differences and confidence intervals further illustrate the magnitude and direction of these changes. Overall, the analysis suggests significant improvements in Purpose and Content aspects from pre-test to post-test, while no significant changes are observed in Evidence and Coherence.

Table 11: Paired samples t test for pre and post test results in experimental group

Paired Samples Test ^a									
		Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	Purpose (Pre-Test) Purpose (Post-Test)	-.809	1.076	.157	-1.124	-.493	-5.150	46	.000
Pair 2	Content (Pre-Test) Content (Post-Test)	-.826	.902	.133	-1.094	-.558	-6.212	45	.000
Pair 3	Evidence (Pre-Test) Evidence (Post-Test)	-.804	.885	.130	-1.067	-.542	-6.165	45	.000
Pair 4	Coherence (Pre-Test) Coherence (Post-Test)	-.457	.721	.106	-.671	-.242	-4.293	45	.000
Pair 5	Cohesion (Pre-Test) Cohesion (Post-Test)	-.426	.715	.104	-.635	-.216	-4.082	46	.000

The provided data showcase the results of paired samples t-tests for pre-test and post-test scores across five different aspects: Purpose, Content, Evidence, Coherence, and Cohesion. Paired differences between pre-test and post-test scores are examined to determine if there are significant changes within each aspect. For all aspects, there are significant mean decreases observed, indicating improvements from pre-test to post-test. Specifically, for Purpose, Content, Evidence, Coherence, and Cohesion, the mean decreases are -0.809, -0.826, -0.804, -0.457, and -0.426 respectively. The t-values range from -5.150 to -4.293 with degrees of freedom ranging from 45 to 46, all resulting in p-values of 0.000. This suggests a high level of significance for all aspects, indicating substantial improvements across the board. The confidence intervals further reinforce the significance of these changes. Overall, the analysis indicates consistent and significant enhancements in all aspects from pre-test to post-test, highlighting the effectiveness of the intervention or educational program being evaluated.

Students' Survey Analysis

To quantify the students' opinions about the potent roles of participating in collaborative activities on a persuasive text using Padlets in learning persuasive writing, data analysis of the 5-linear scale questionnaire of 15 items was implemented.

Respondents were asked if learning persuasive essay writing using Padlets helps in having enough time to share opinion and learning from peers (1.2), and in reducing anxiety in learning about persuasive writing (1.3). As shown in Figure 1, more than 82% agree, while less than 8% disagree.

Figure 1. PA: learning from peers and reducing anxiety

When the respondents were asked if learning persuasive essay writing using Padlets helps in monitoring the learning process (1.4), the majority showed agreement with 64.7%. Only 5.9% disagreed, while 33.3% revealed neutral stance. Then, when asked whether it helps in producing better work knowing that other students read the comments (1.5), the overwhelming majority of 70.6 % affirmed, whereas around 13.8% disagreed. Figure 2 below depicts the results.

Figure 2. PA: monitoring the learning process and producing better work

Then, when the respondents were asked if learning persuasive essay writing using Padlets helps in triggering their motivation to write better (1.6), and in changing their attitudes towards the complexity of learning about writing (1.7), the results showed that the majority agreed that the pedagogy makes them more motivated (86.4%) and more positive (64.7%) as opposed to (3.9%) who disagreed on the claim that it triggers their motivation to write better. 5.9% also disagreed on the idea that using Genre Based Pedagogy (GBP) and Padlet Application (PA) can change their attitudes towards the complexity of learning about writing. Figure 3 below illustrates the results.

Figure 3. PA: motivation and attitudes towards writing

The second section of the questionnaire aims at quantifying responses on the level of understanding the linguistic textual quality (coherence and cohesion) and the rhetorical features (purpose, persuasive reasons and appeals: logos, ethos and pathos). When asked whether participating in the collaborative activities on a persuasive text using Padlets helps in understanding what is occurring in the text (2.1) and how the text is organized (2.2), only 3.9% showed disagreement. As shown in Figure 4, the overwhelming majority of more than 90% agreed.

Figure 4. PA and text understanding

Respondents were also asked if the approach helps in capturing interest in noticing linguistic features of using descriptive words, graded vocabulary and persuasive phrases to maintain coherence in persuasion (2.3), and in constructing knowledge about the organization of a text via viewing peers’ graphic organizers (2.4). The overwhelming majority of more than 70% agreed. This result confirms the potent roles of the approach in capturing interest to notice the features and the organization of the text. Figure 5 below depicts the results.

Figure 5. PA: noticing linguistic features and the organization of a text

Other results depicted the students' responses to the statement "participating in collaborative activities on a persuasive text using Padlets helps in capturing interest in understanding basic rhetorical appeals including Pathos, Ethos, and Logos to persuade (2.5), and in leading to the gradual control of rhetorical and linguistic features based on initial understanding (2.6)". 7.8 % disagreed, while around 50% provided their agreement. Moreover, 33.3% strongly agreed that the approach captured their interest to understand about Pathos, Ethos and Logos, while 17.6% strongly agreed that it leads them to the gradual control of the features. Figure 6 below shows the results.

Figure 6. PA: controlling rhetorical and linguistic features

While statement (2.7) depicts the responses to the statement “Participating in collaborative activities on a persuasive text using Padlets helps in directing the mind towards the use of the forms of language to produce effective writing that is coherent and purposeful”, the minority of 3.9% provided a disagreement response, followed by 25.5% of neutral stance. However, the majority of 49% agreed, and 21.6% showed their strong agreement. Regarding their input on whether the collaborative activities help in learning about building texts independently (2.8), the students revealed great agreement; as shown in Figure 7, 45%.1 strongly agreed and 37.3% agreed, making the percentage of agreement 82.4%.

Figure 7. PA: producing coherent and purposeful writing and building texts

Students’ Reflection Logs Analysis

The results from the data analysis of the 51 students’ reflection logs, in which they answered 5 open ended questions, yielded a number of outcomes including the students’ attitudes on their experience with the intervention of SFL-GBP using microblogging Padlet Application (PA), mainly in enhancing their understanding to linguistic features and rhetorical features, and in affecting their learning process to write a persuasive genre essay at the university level. All students’ responses on these outcomes in addition to their feelings and recommendations were transcribed and interpreted accordingly. The responses are combined in the following outcomes and a sample of what was stated, whether they shared consensus or disagreed, was reported.

Outcome 1: To determine to what extent microblogging Padlet Application (PA) technology and genre based pedagogy can affect EFL Lebanese students’ persuasive essay writing with respect to linguistic and rhetorical features

Question 1: How do the writing instruction tasks you participated in using Padlets enhance your understanding to linguistic features?

✓ The visual organization included in the activities on the Padlets helps me get sufficient understanding of the given text.
✓ The tasks help me know about the organizational structure of the text.
✓ The tasks draw my attention to the importance of using transitions and repeating key words in the text.
✓ I enjoyed searching for more key words, transitions, and synonyms that my friend shared in his/her post.

✓ I learned to notice the purpose, the audience, why the text is written, and how it is written. The first task pushes me to think more about the author's purpose and the convincing reasons.
✓ Participating in writing tasks using Padlets offers more time to be able to understand and focus on linguistic features and to include them more in my writing.
✓ By searching for linguistic features to include on the wall, I referred to the answers posted by the colleagues to check my understanding.
✓ Using Padlets helps us understand linguistic features; by searching for answers to share, we learn more.

(32/51 or 62.7 %) showed their excitement about writing on Padlets. They said it was the first time they wrote online about what they read. They were learning new information and writing about it on Padlets which provides a visual representation of content, making it easier to organize and categorize linguistic features.

Question 2: How do the writing instruction tasks you participated in using microblogging Padlet Application (PA) enhance your understanding of rhetorical features?

✓ The activities help me notice why the text is written and how to make my writing credible by adding ethos, pathos, and logos.
✓ I enjoyed searching for more convincing reasons that my friends posted online.
✓ The Padlet tasks help me check my understanding about ethos, pathos, and logos.
✓ Now, I learned that we can include our experience and stories as Pathos.
✓ I valued the importance of including numbers and emotions to convince others to change their point of view about a topic.
✓ It helps me learn how to write; the guided activities on Padlets helped me to know about the organizational structure of my writing.

(21/51 or 41.17 %) showed their satisfaction with the tasks that were given to them. They said, “checking our information about Logos, Ethos, and Pathos by reading peers’ responses confirms our understanding. It was the first time we learn from each other’s answers at our pace.” They were learning new information collaboratively, and this facilitates understanding.

Outcome 2: To determine the EFL Lebanese students’ attitudes towards the use of microblogging Padlet Application (PA) and the genre-based pedagogy in learning to write persuasive genre essay at the university level

Question 3: To what extent does your participation in the wall activities posted on Padlet affect your learning to write a persuasive genre essay at a university level?

✓ The sections or columns for different aspects of persuasive writing aid in a clearer understanding of the components.
✓ My engagement at my pace helps me learn from others and makes me responsible since I know that the teacher is not the only one who is going to read my answers.
✓ Working on small tasks day after another helps me deepen my understanding about how to think well to find information to convince others.
✓ When I read answers posted by my peers, I made sure about my understanding.
✓ From simple tasks in which we commented on the components of a persuasive essay, I learned what to include in my essay.
✓ Padlet gave me an opportunity to be responsible for my answers and to learn from my peers' thoughts.
✓ I learned that when I look at how others think, I learn wider.
✓ I feel free and comfortable towards using Padlets; we are in the 21 st century and every one prefers writing online than writing on papers; this gives us more freedom to think and learn about our mistakes.

(23/51 or 45.09 %) showed their agreement that their participation in the wall activities posted on Padlet affects their learning of the elements of the persuasive essay in an interesting and interactive way, away from books and boring methods. It reduces the risk of feeling embarrassed and nervous.

Question 4: How do you feel towards using Padlets in learning writing at the university level?

✓ Learning writing needs practice and feedback; thus, it was a great experience to learn about essay writing through responding to short tasks and writing chunks and getting feedback on our thoughts from peers.
✓ Learning writing is somehow boring, yet through online activities, I felt motivated and so much engaged.
✓ Padlets gave me an opportunity to learn from peers and add to my knowledge before producing my ideas.
✓ Working on Padlets helps me to produce a text easily as each activity ensures my understanding of what to include in the essay.
✓ It helped me become confident to build my essay independently.
✓ I love it; it created an open collaborative communication.
✓ It captured my interest in persuading others.

✓	It reduces my anxiety in practicing a persuasive essay in a limited time; learning from peers helped me write better.
✓	Through guided writing, I showed great interest to be actively involved. It is great because I wrote the information I have learned; this deepens understanding and moves information to long term memory.
✓	A Padlet helps students at university level; it improves the skill of being self-assured, and it saves time.
✓	Using Padlets helps the student to be more productive in writing essays.

(34/51 or 66.6 %) showed positive feeling towards using Padlets in learning writing at the university level; they asserted that their participation in the wall activities posted on Padlets reduced their anxiety and boosted their motivation to get engaged. This outcome is confirmed by their reflection on question 5 in which they expressed whether they recommend using Padlets in other courses. 90% of the students showed agreement that this approach establishes an environment of open collaboration and communication, engaging students' interest in making experiential, interpersonal, and textual meanings to persuade, reduces anxiety in practicing a persuasive discourse and learning from peers, and yields better essay writing. Below are samples of the students' input:

✓	Yes, I recommend using Padlets in other courses and domains because it helps us learn from each other's answers.
✓	Although it is online, I understand more because there are opportunities for solving exercises at our pace at any time.
✓	Padlet tool gives enough time to think at our pace, understand, see friends' answers, and then add our ideas.
✓	It helps the student learn more by looking at the answers of other students and learn more before giving out the answer.
✓	It helps students have equal opportunities to look at various answers, think, and compose answers without feeling stressed or embarrassed.

Discussion and Conclusion

The findings, as well as the academic references, strongly support the idea of using microblogging Padlet Application (PA) and Genre Based Pedagogy (GBP) within the Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL) Framework to extend the knowledge of linguistic and rhetoric techniques to create a text. Consistent with Yasuda, 2015; Syarifah & Gunawan, 2015; Nagoa, 2019; Abdel-Malek, 2019 who adopted GBP in teaching writing, the overall qualitative and quantitative analysis of the data revealed that learners enhanced their understanding of the logico-semantic relationship and gained awareness of the ideational, interpersonal, and textual features within target genre texts. Transforming didactic form of teaching and learning into innovative pedagogy plays a potent role in extending knowledge of persuasive linguistic features and rhetorical appeals. When students collaborated in activities on noticing rhetorical appeals and linguistic features of a text using microblogging Padlet Application (PA), they became equipped with enough conventions that improve their writing. This supports the idea of Humphrey and Macnaught (2016) who reported that GBP enhances the overall writing performance and with Widodo (2016), Hsu and Liu (2019), and Rohayati (2020) who studied the teaching of writing using genre-based pedagogy with technological assistance and revealed that the implementation of GBP with digital tools could make the teaching of writing more interesting and help students construct their genre writing interactively. The results also align with Yousefifard and Fathi (2021) who found that the blog-mediated pedagogy is effective and viable as it contributes to enhancing the motives of English language learners and in yielding better linguistic and effective outcomes in English language classes.

Thus, using PA and practicing the SFL-GBP fosters an atmosphere of collaborative communication climate, captures students' interest in making experiential, interpersonal, and textual meanings to persuade, reduces anxiety in practicing a persuasive discourse and learning from peers, and yields better essay writing. It assists learners to recognize the linguistics features and schematic structures related to the purpose, audience, and the context of a persuasive discourse. This includes understanding the reasons behind their writing, identifying their audience, and mastering the techniques of effective writing. As Hyland (2003&2007) proved, it helps probe into the functions of language as a system of choice and interact with others to generate a coherent message. It shows great effectiveness on developing the organizational structure of the students' writing.

It is anticipated that the outcomes of this study will fill in the gap and give teachers, educators, and trainers a solid foundation for comprehending the potential benefits of blogging in the Lebanese university EFL classrooms. Instructors at the university level have to reconfigure the ways that they interact with students and thus undergo a shift from the instruction paradigm to the learning paradigm that includes digital collaborative blogging activities.

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Appendix A

Pre-post Test

Equality between males and females is considered as a sign of civilization and progress, yet many adopt a more traditional attitude which gives more privileges to males.

	<p>Read the discussion on the Pros and Cons of Promoting Gender. In a persuasive essay of 400-500 words, discuss why men and women should or should not be treated equally in social, economic, or any two aspects of society.</p>
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Appendix B Rubric for the Assessment of the Persuasive Essay

	CRITERIA	Advanced (4pts)	Proficient (3pts)	Progressing (2pts)	Beginning (1pt)
1.PURPOSE	Rhetorical feature: Purpose 1.1.Topic 1.2.Thesis 1.3.Context 1.4.Audience 1.5.Genre	The persuasive writing demonstrates advanced and comprehensive understanding of purpose. This is characterised by an exceptionally clear and insightful : - topic - thesis that is well-developed in relation to the context, audience, and genre.	The persuasive writing demonstrates a sound understanding of purpose. This is characterised by a clear : - topic - thesis that is developed in relation to the context, audience, and genre.	The persuasive writing demonstrates a basic understanding of purpose. This is characterised by some evidence of a : - topic - thesis that relates to the context, audience, and genre.	The persuasive writing demonstrates a very limited understanding of purpose. This is characterised by an inaccurate or unidentifiable : - topic and/or - thesis that is poorly developed.
2.CONTENT	Rhetorical feature: 2.1 Reasons	The persuasive writing demonstrates a comprehensive and relevant selection of content and reasons. This is characterized by consistently relevant , accurate and authoritative reasons.	The persuasive writing demonstrates a sound and relevant selection of content and reasons. This is characterized by frequently relevant , accurate and authoritative reasons.	The persuasive writing demonstrates a basic yet relevant selection of content and reasons. This is characterized by occasionally relevant , accurate and authoritative reasons.	The persuasive writing demonstrates a very limited and/or irrelevant selection of content and reasons. This is characterized by irrelevant information and data inaccurate reasons.
3.EVIDENCE	Rhetorical features: Appeals 3.1.Logos 3.2.Ethos 3.3.Pathos	The persuasive writing demonstrates a convincing analysis and synthesis of evidence . This is characterized by consistent use of: -Logos (statistics/cause-effect/descriptive example) - Ethos (firsthand experience/anecdote) - Pathos (emotive language/inclusive language)	The persuasive writing demonstrates a sound analysis and synthesis of evidence . This is characterized by frequent use of: -Logos (statistics/cause-effect/descriptive example) - Ethos (firsthand experience/anecdote) - Pathos (emotive language/inclusive language)	The persuasive writing demonstrates a basic analysis and synthesis of evidence . This is characterized by occasional use of: -Logos (statistics/cause-effect/descriptive example) - Ethos (firsthand experience/anecdote) - Pathos (emotive language/inclusive language)	The persuasive writing demonstrates a very limited analysis and synthesis of evidence . This is characterised by: - illogical logos - over-generalised ethos - lack of pathos
4.COHERENCE	Linguistic Features: Organizational Structure of essay and paragraphs 4.1.hook 4.2.body Paragraphs 4.3.closure 4.4.cohesive Ties	The persuasive writing demonstrates consistent and conventional structuring and sequencing of paragraphs that demonstrates a highly appropriate and conventional language. This is characterized by logical compelling progression of: - introduction & hook - 2 body paragraphs that explain main ideas using descriptive language, graded vocabulary, persuasive phrases, modalities and authoritative voice, - closure that summarizes the main topics without repeating previous sentences and presents the writer's opinions and suggestions for change - cohesive ties.	The persuasive writing demonstrates a sound structuring and sequencing of paragraphs that demonstrates an appropriate and conventional language. This is characterized by developed progression of : - introduction & hook - 2 body paragraphs that explain main ideas using descriptive language, graded vocabulary, persuasive phrases, modalities and authoritative voice, - closure that summarizes the main topics without repeating previous sentences and presents the writer's opinions and suggestions for change - cohesive ties	The persuasive writing demonstrates a basic structuring and sequencing of paragraphs that generally demonstrates an appropriate and conventional language. This is characterized by some unconventional and inaccurate presentation of: - introduction & hook - 2 body paragraphs that explain main ideas using descriptive language, graded vocabulary, persuasive phrases, modalities and authoritative voice, - closure that summarizes the main topics without repeating previous sentences and presents the writer's opinions and suggestions for change - cohesive ties	The persuasive writing demonstrates a very limited structuring and sequencing of content that demonstrates an inappropriate and unconventional language. This is characterised by incomplete or inaccurate presentation of: - introduction & hook - 2 body paragraphs that explain main ideas using descriptive language, graded vocabulary, persuasive phrases, modalities and authoritative voice, - closure that summarizes the main topics without repeating previous sentences and presents the writer's opinions and suggestions for change - cohesive ties
5.Cohesion	Linguistic Features: Cohesion Devices 5.1. transition signals 5.2. repeated words 5.3 reference words 5.4 synonyms	The persuasive writing demonstrates complex and conventional cohesion. This is characterized by consistent and conventional use of: - transitions - repeated key words - reference words - synonyms	The persuasive writing demonstrates sound and conventional cohesion This is characterized by frequent use of conventional and accurate: - transitions - repeated key words - reference words - synonyms	The persuasive writing demonstrates conventional but basic cohesion. This is characterized by some incorrect or unconventional use of: - transitions - repeated key words - reference words - synonyms	The persuasive writing demonstrates inappropriate and unconventional cohesion. This is characterized by frequently incorrect or unconventional use of: - transitions - repeated key words - reference words - synonyms

Total points : _____ /20

Perry, K. (2012). *Interactive rubric for written communication*. James Cook University. <https://libguides.jcu.edu.au/irwc/rubric>

Rabour, L. (2023). *Persuasive techniques & rhetoric (Logos, Ethos, Pathos)*. OER Commons. <https://oercommons.org/authoring/55399-persuasive-techniques-rhetoric-logos-ethos-pathos>

Appendix C

Student Questionnaire

We are interested to know about your attitudes on your experience with the intervention of SFL- GBP using Padlets, mainly in noticing the indicators of textual quality and persuasive appeals of rhetorical features, and in affecting the learning process to write a persuasive genre essay at the university level. **Please, indicate to which extent you agree or disagree with the following statements: 1 (strongly agree), 2 (agree), 3 (neutral), 4 (disagree), 5 (strongly disagree).**

Statements	1	2	3	4	5
Learning persuasive essay writing using Padlets helps in					
1.1 creating an open collaborative communication climate					
1.2 having enough time to share opinion and learning from peers					
1.3 reducing anxiety in learning about persuasive writing					
1.4 monitoring the learning process					
1.5 producing better work knowing that other students read my comments					
1.6 triggering my motivation to write better					
1.7 changing the attitudes towards the complexity of learning about writing					
Participating in collaborative activities on a persuasive text using Padlets helps in					
2.1 providing more time for understanding what is occurring in the text					
2.2 providing more time for understanding how the text is organized					
2.3 capturing interest in noticing linguistic features of using descriptive words, graded vocabulary and persuasive phrases to maintain coherence in persuasion					
2.4 constructing knowledge about the organization of a text via viewing peers' graphic organizers					
2.5 capturing interest in understanding basic rhetorical appeals including Pathos, Ethos, and Logos to persuade					
2.6 leading to the gradual control of rhetorical and linguistic features based on initial understanding					
2.7 directing the mind towards the use of the forms of language to produce effective writing that is coherent and purposeful					
2.8 learning about building texts independently					

Appendix D

Intervention II: Persuasion and Evidence

Nadine Joudi + 17 • 10h

II. Persuasion & Evidence : Rhetorical Appeals

Reread the persuasive essay about Artificial Intelligence, and then complete the four components of the rhetorical features you identified. To know more about LOGOS,ETHOS&PATHOS, refer to <https://stlc.edu/student-support/academic-success-and-tutoring/writing-center/writing-resources/pathos-logos-and-ethos.asp>

2.1 LOGOS

Hassan Hamdan 10h

Evan Parez support his words by using numbers and dates like how was people who sold DVD fearedfor their life when Netflix started streaming movies in 2007. And about the changes of early 2000s and 2010s,it changed us from the ancient area to Ai

☆ Rate 0

Add comment

Anonymous 11h

to appeal to the audiences' sense of reason or logic, the author makes clear, logical connections between ideas such as (instead of sending humans into debris and destruction during times of disaster, robotics and artificial intelligence can be used to complete dangerous tasks such as disaster rescue) and includes the use of facts and statistics such as (When Netflix started streaming movies in 2007, people who sold DVDs feared for their life, and when music streaming services like Napster rose up, record and CD vendors panicked. When the first iPhone was unveiled by Steve Jobs, cellphone companies were given a run for their money for sure). Using historical and literal analogies to make a logical argument is another strategy such as the dates used (2007,2000,2010).

☆ Rate 0

Add comment

Anonymous 1d

Sarah EISaleh

The writer used numbers (dates) to show how the revolution of technology is evolving into a new era of change. He mentions some examples from the year 2007 talking about how people who sold DVDs were sitting in fear for losing their business. He also talks about the changes of the early 2000s and 2010s where he talks about how these changes amazed us.

Moreover, the writer used facts. For instance, "There have been a lot of tasks that have become automated, particularly assembly line production tasks." "Assembly lines are prone to human error."

☆ Rate 0

Add comment

Farah Eid 12d

the author talked about the technological wave that happens throughout history such as when Netflix started streaming movies in 2007, people who sold DVDs feared for their lives, or when music

2.2 ETHOS

Hassan Hamdan 10h

The writer tell us his professional experience about how much he wasted time before using Ai and he explain how he barely had time to actual work because of the amount of time and hard work he needed and solve the problems he encountered.Also how he should repeat tasks constantly.

☆ Rate 0

Add comment

Anonymous 11h

To demonstrate that she have fairly examined the issue, the author mentioned her own experience when she said (I say this because I worked in a data science role where I was working with machine learning. There were times when I was spending hours trying to search for a solution to a problem I was trying to solve or repeating a redundant task, resulting in some days only allowing me to do actual work for a few hours instead of making progress the entire day)

☆ Rate 0

Add comment

Anonymous 1d

Sarah EISaleh

The writer shared his personal experience with working with machine learning in data science role which required a lot of work. He explains how he barely had anytime to do actual work because of how much time it took him and hard labor to find the information he needed and solved the problems he had. He also mentions how he had to do repetitive tasks continuously.

☆ Rate 0

Add comment

Farah Eid 12d

the author mentioned his personal experience as he referred to his work in a data science role.

☆ Rate 0

Add comment

Anonymous 12d

He mentioned his personal experiences in the article

☆ Rate 0

Add comment

Anonymous 12d

Ethos

Personal experience in data science role
Expert opinion * Kashyap Vyas *
Rola Al-Draini

2.3 Pathos

Hassan Hamdan 10h

The writer wanted to make the reader feel the way he wanted by giving him his dose in some way,also he struck a chord with the reader such as his use of grief terms.

☆ Rate 0

Add comment

Anonymous 11h

to persuade an audience by purposely evoking certain emotions to make them feel the way the author wants them to feel, Authors make deliberate word choices, such as (i cried)

☆ Rate 0

Add comment

Anonymous 1d

Sarah EISaleh

The writer used Pathos. For instance when he said, "I cried." Which pulled me as a reader closer to his purpose where it explains how much he suffered during his time of working without the artificial intelligence.

☆ Rate 0

Add comment

Farah Eid 12d

the author made the audience connect with his argument by using pathos such mentioning the lives that could've been saved if people were able to send in machines to control the damage instead of human. Or asking the audience to imagine all lengthy tasks that eat up hours of their day, making them wish they just had more time to get real work done.

☆ Rate 0

Add comment

Anonymous 12d

The writer in this article showed us his feeling in several sentences,in order to create emotional connection with tge reader's emotions.

☆ Rate 0

Add comment

Anonymous 12d

Pathos

Language Choice
Emotional Scenarios
Narrative of personal experience
Rola Al-Draini

☆ Rate 0

2.4 Other Rhetorical Devices

Hassan Hamdan 10h

-imagery
-Analogies

☆ Rate 0

Add comment

Anonymous 11h

The author used other rhetorical devices such as questions and using the word imagine

☆ Rate 0

Add comment

Anonymous 1d

Sarah EISaleh

The writer asked questions like, "Surely these changes would come to pass, they're just hot trends, right?"

"Have you ever wished you could get help on something at anytime of the day?"

☆ Rate 0

Add comment

Anonymous 12d

Other rhetorical devices

Rhetorical questions
Analogy
Rola Al-Draini

☆ Rate 0

Add comment

Anonymous 13d

He uses powerful statements,linguistic features,authority,statistics, personal stories , reasons and explanations questions at the end

Raghda Arheli

☆ Rate 0

Add comment

Anonymous 13d

Other rhetorical devices are the words that attracted the reader like imagining needing a study buddy that constantly searches the internet for sources and material while you sleep and then gives you a concise summary containing only the essentials for an exam.

Khaled Awad

☆ Rate 0

Add comment

Mrs. Nadine Joudi is a university instructor and an Education Trainer in Lebanon. In addition to teaching Education and English courses at the college level, she frequently facilitates workshops and coaches teachers. Nadine serves as a Middle East Professional Learning Initiative convener with Professional Education at the Harvard Graduate School of Education. Alongside her teaching and training duties, she is pursuing a PhD in Linguistics and holds two Master's degrees in Teaching English and in Educational Leadership. She is also an active researcher. Her published articles cover subjects such as peace education, civic engagement, gender leadership styles and linguistic practices, and humor in EFL classes. Additionally, she has papers forthcoming on AI as well as blogging in EFL.

Dr. Nawal Nabih Ayoub a scholar in the realm of language studies, holds a PhD in English Language and Linguistics. With a solid academic foundation, Dr. Nawal completed a Master's degree in Education and TESL, following a Bachelor's in English Literature and languages. Dr. Nawal is a university instructor, course leader, school teacher, and coordinator of English language programs. She has also lent her expertise as a researcher and a curriculum designer, further solidifying her reputation as a thought leader in the field.

